

Omissions, ambiguities in, and misinterpretations of 1D regional Earth conductivity models on which NERC TPL-007-1 Table 3 “beta” (β) scaling factors rely— January 2018

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Abstract. NERC’s TPL 7 (see Glossary, Page 14) ground conductivity (β) scaling factors¹ rely on Earth conductivity estimates assembled quickly for EPRI in 20 1D models by Dr. Peter Fernberg (“an independent researcher from Ottawa”) and published in 2012.² These *default* scaling factors and their underlying 1D models suffer from omissions, ambiguities, misinterpretations — identified here and tabulated in Appendix A — which merit attention because TPL 7 allows planners for regulated entities to use different “specific earth model(s) with documented justification.” This paper does not address pros and cons of 1D, 2D, 3D models and their assumptions. This paper may support improvement of Earth conductivity models, a high priority for NERC.³

Introduction. Dr. Fernberg produced 20 1D models (relating them to 19 regions) in his 2012 EPRI Report. See Appendix E. EPRI and Dr. Fernberg deemed them a first approximation to Earth response in parts of the US based on review of literature at that time. EPRI’s contract directed him to finish quickly (EPRI 2012).⁴ He drew on his background (e.g., Fernberg et al 2007, Fernberg 2011) and earlier Canadian surveys (see Ferguson 1998).

NERC wanted 1D models of Earth conductivity produced for study by its GMD Task Force.⁵ Dr. Fernberg’s 1D models were not prepared in order to support NERC reliability standards.⁶ As published in 2012, they were not definitive enough or in a format usable for NERC standards development. In 2014, USGS interpreted EPRI’s tables, resolved discrepancies, and provided machine-readable files for NERC to plug into 1D software, warning, however, that “these conductivity profiles ... should not be considered ‘definitive’, or even self-consistent.”⁷

USGS also prepared a 1D model for peninsular Florida which was published as an Open File Report (USGS 2015, 20 PDF pages). But the 20 1D models published in 2012 were not USGS models, even though Dr. Fernberg had communicated with USGS scientists about them starting in 2011.

Although relation of Earth conductivity to vulnerability of electric power systems had aroused international interest by 1970 (McKay 2003, page 3 and References at pages 219-238), I trace specific history of EPRI’s 2012 Report to events in 2010-2011, including maps and otherwise-proprietary 1D models in two companion, January 2010, Metatech reports responsive to FERC and Oak Ridge National Laboratory (Gilbert et al 2010, Figs. 2-20, 2-22; Kappenman 2010, Fig. 1-6).

¹ NERC Reliability Standard TPL-007-1 (NERC TPL 7), Attachment 1, Table 3, sometimes called β (“beta”) factors.

² One-Dimensional Earth Resistivity Models for Selected Areas of Continental United States & Alaska, <https://www.epri.com/#/pages/product/00000000001026430/>. Technical update, December 2012. “A Technical Update report is intended as an informal report of continuing research, a meeting, or a topical study. It is not a final EPRI technical report.” EPRI acknowledged “support” of USGS and “assistance” of D. Boteler and L. Tritchchenko of Natural Resources Canada. “This report describes research sponsored by EPRI” prepared “under contract with” EPRI.

³ NERC’s forthcoming TPL-007-2 proposal, not yet submitted to FERC, is also beyond the scope of this paper.

⁴ EPRI’s February 27, 2012, contract with Dr. Fernberg called for completion by May 31, 2012. Dr. Fernberg’s work was part of a broader joint project between NERC, EPRI, the USGS Geomagnetism Program, Natural Resources Canada and the USGS Crustal Geophysics and Geochemistry program. See Appendix B. Dr. Fernberg set out to produce a coarse 1D regional conductivity map of the United States from existing studies and a 1D conductivity model for each physiographic province. Deliverables included preliminary 1D conductivity models from several physiographic provinces in January 2012 and a discretized US map with 1D conductivity and known conductivity boundaries.

⁵ NERC’s Board of Trustees endorsed creation of a GMD Task Force in November 2010. It was formed early in 2011. EPRI participated from the start. Dr. David Boteler of Natural Resources Canada, a scientist who had worked with utility engineers, was invited to participate. So were U.S. Government departments and agencies including DOE, NASA, and NOAA with its Space Weather Prediction Center (SWPC). EPRI’s GMD-related research involvement went back to Quebec’s 1989 blackout (EPRI 2011).

⁶ Not until October 2012 did FERC issue *Reliability Standards for Geomagnetic Disturbances, Notice of Proposed Rulemaking*, 77 FR 64,935 (Oct. 24, 2012), 141 FERC ¶ 61,045 (2012) (NOPR).

⁷ USGS 2014 explained and disclaimed in introductory README.txt: “Finally, these conductivity profiles are based on literature reviews, NOT on any single field study or campaign. As such, they should not be considered “definitive”, or even self-consistent.”

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Figure 1-6. Multiple 1-D ground models for the U.S. grid.

The latter endorsed sufficiency of 1D Modeling (Kappenman 2010, page 1-7). 8

Dr. Fernberg’s map & 1D model locations. Figure 1-1 (like Table 1-1) of EPRI’s 2012 Report (below) shows locations of 1D Earth resistivity models (marked by yellow circles) in 19 of 30 mapped physiographic regions of CONUS. Eleven mapped regions have no model. (One location has two models.) Model locations are often at a corner or edge of their regions. Table 1-1 confirms that resistivity estimates Dr. Fernberg found in the literature covered only limited areas, as explained in his Introduction (excerpted in Appendix C) and dozen chapters of text. See Appendix A, a comparative tabulation of issues, starting with USGS physiographic regions map (below; see EPRI 2012, Figs. 5-1 and 13-1):

Figure 1-1 Location of 1D Earth Resistivity Models with Respect to Physiographic Regions of the Contiguous United States.

File:US physiographic regions map.jpg

Table 1-1 Model Numbers for Each Physiographic Region (Chapter #s in Parentheses)

Model	Physiographic Description	Model	Physiographic Description
AK-1	Adirondack Mountains (New York) (1)	IP-1	Interior Plains (North Dakota) (8)
AP-1	Appalachian Plateau (5)	IP-2	Interior Plains (North American Conductive Anomaly) (8)
AP-2	Appalachian Plateau (Northern Portion) (6)	IP-3	Interior Plains (Michigan) (9)
BR-1	Northwest Basin and Range (Oregon) (11)	IP-4	Interior Plains (Great Plains Province) (13)
CL-1	Colorado Plateau (12)	NE-1	New England (Maine) (4)
CO-1	Columbia Plateau (11)	PB-1	Pacific Border (Willamette Valley, Oregon) (11)
CP-1	Coastal Plain (South Carolina) (5)	PB-2	Pacific Border (Puget Lowlands, Washington) (11)
CP-2	Coastal Plain (Georgia) (7)	PT-1	Piedmont (5)
CS-1	Cascade-Sierra Mountains (Oregon, Washington) (11)	SL-1	St. Lawrence Lowlands (New York) (3)
		SU-1	Superior Uplands (Minnesota, Wisconsin, Upper Michigan) (10)

8 “1.2 Ground Models and Electric Field Calculation. In order to compute the induced currents flowing in a power network, it is necessary to be able to establish the electric fields induced in the Earth by variations in the geomagnetic field. ... Past experience has indicated that 1-D Earth conductivity models are sufficient to compute the local electric fields. Because there is considerable heterogeneity in conductivity over North America, multiple 1-D models can be used where the conductivity variations are extremely large.”

Omissions, ambiguities in EPRI’s 2012 1D models supporting NERC TPL7 β factor

EPRI’s 190-page 2012 Report covered 19 “selected areas” of the contiguous United States (called Earth conductivity regions) — flagging that limited data were stretched to represent some large areas. See map, above, Fig. 1-1 from that Report, and its Table 1-1 (left). (NERC later divided one of those 19 into two regions.) EPRI’s 2012 Report drew upon a much finer, more detailed mapping of physiographic regions used by USGS since 1917.⁹ See second map, above.¹⁰

USGS simplified that traditional map in 2011 into a coarser, 24-region CONUS map with red boundaries (left),¹¹ prepared by Dr. Paul A. Bedrosian of USGS Crustal Geophysics and Geochemistry Science Center. Dr. Fernberg split four of the 24 regions, dividing AP, CP, and PB into two parts each and IP into four parts. And he presented two models for two geologic parts of AK without a geographic split.¹²

In August 2012, EPRI used this map with the addition of circles locating six 1D models (for SL-1, AK-1, AP-2, AP-1, PT-1, CP-1) on three slides (GMDTF 2012c, PDF pages 33-35, 37, 38). AP-2 was marked by a yellow circle (the other five by white circles). Boundaries were not shown splitting the AP and CP regions.

Boundary stretching. Originally Dr. Fernberg appears to have limited geographic applicability of his 20 1D models, as reflected in Table 1-1 of EPRI’s 2012 Report and in its text. See also its maps for Atlantic Plain and Appalachian Highlands (at page 5-3), Interior Plains (page 8-5), Lower Michigan (page 9-6), Superior Upland (page 10-4), Pacific Northwest (page 11-2), Interior Plains (page 13-2).

In August 2012 Dr. Jennifer Gannon of USGS Geomagnetism Program called attention to coverage of only a fraction of CONUS, using the 24-region map with additions (as shown below).

Conductivity –
US Physiographic Regions

Her slide illustrated nine completed 1D models (white circles), four in progress (yellow circles), one model pending (blue oblong), and four “model area proposed” (dashed green rectangles). GMDTF 2012c, PDF page 72. No boundaries are shown between AP-1 and AP-2 or CP-1 and CP-2. IP-3 is marked by dashed white lines. Yellow-and-red dashed lines mark parts of BR-1, CO-1, CS-1, and PB-1 common boundaries and yellow-only dashed lines Mark splits of BR-1, CS-1, PB-1. IP-4 does not appear.

A new model (IP-4) was eventually created for the western part of the GREAT PLAINS green rectangle, but not for the eastern part or the other three green rectangles.

⁹ PHYSIOGRAPHIC REGIONS OF THE LOWER 48 UNITED STATES, <https://www.nrc.gov/docs/ML0933/ML093340269.pdf>

¹⁰ USGS’s detailed physiographic system divides CONUS into eight Regions which it divides into 25 Provinces, most of which it further divides into Sections. My count of 71 are the Sections in CONUS plus three Provinces with no Sections. (I do not count the Atlantic Continental Shelf Province or the Northern Section of the St. Lawrence Valley Province.)

¹¹ EPRI later used that map to illustrate a slide entitled “Validate 1-D conductivity model of all physiographic regions in North America” (GMDTF 2013, Day 1 PDF 79, EPRI Slide 12).

¹² He also presented two AK models (while listing only one in Table 1-1): AK-1,2 on Fig. 1-1 and AK-1A and AK-1B in text.

Evolution of boundaries is reflected by dashed white lines (some incomplete for new regions) and dotted white lines (for split regions) in an April 2013 NERC - TVA slide about GIC Model Validation.¹³

Models CL-1, IP-3 and IP-4 showed up.

I have not learned how the boundary stretching proceeded during 2012, leading up to EPRI's Report published in December.

TPL 7 comparative map (below) compares 24 simplified regions (red or dashed red boundaries) with TPL "beta" (β) Scaling Factor regions (dashed or dotted white boundaries, the latter marking a split). This map is in the NERC Standard itself (TPL 7, Attachment 1, Figure 1). I assume USGS prepared it, using red and white line GoogleEarth layers.

USGS online reference site. USGS Geomagnetism Program posted the TPL 7 red and white dashed-line regional resistivity models map, a link to EPRI's 2012 Report, and links to 19 regions (arranged alphabetically, USGS 2014a). Each of these 19 links provided:

- a short descriptive text by USGS citing model source as Fernberg, EPRI 2012 (except for FL-1);
- a map with USGS boundary interpretation;
- a 1D model layer-cake diagram (two in the case of AK-1);
- a uniform disclaimer¹⁴ and a link to machine-readable file for that model.

For example, for New England: "Model NE-1 represents southwest portion of Maine, just north of Portland, and more generally the New England physiographic province. [Fernberg, EPRI 2012]" USGS conformed some of the 1-page models of EPRI's 2012 Report to its more extensive tables which it deemed more accurate.

Discussion.

Assembling 1D ground conductivity models "for all physiographic regions" was important to NERC in 2012.¹⁵ EPRI's 190-page 2012 Report collected estimates (sometimes not consistent) of resistivity/conductivity and thickness for layers of Earth crust and upper mantle, in text, tables, and 1D models (one-page, layer-cake diagrams) for most of the 24 regions, a few of which it split up. It often showed ranges of estimates, sometimes selecting midpoints.

Omissions. Several regions were not covered at all, whether for lack of data or lack of time. TPL 7 allows use of a scaling factor for an adjacent region. That may have been expedient, but it was not justified by a scientific or technical rationale in TPL 7 or in EPRI's 2012 Report.

Stretches. Some boundaries of model applicability were stretched far from the model locations without rationale. For example, consider IP-1 Interior Plains (North Dakota) stretching to Ohio and Texas. Also consider three other regions mapped below, PB-1 Pacific Border (Willamette Valley); BR-1 Basin and Range (Oregon); and CP-2 Coastal Plain (Georgia):

¹³ GMDTF 2013, slide 4 ("Example of working with utilities and USGS to calibrate GIC and earth conductivity models").

¹⁴ "Resistivity values and depths have been interpreted from published geological reports and maps, and may differ from actual conditions measured by a geophysical survey and/or borehole."

¹⁵ In February 2012 the GMD Task Force released an Interim Special Reliability Assessment, with followup in June (NERC GMDTF 2012a and 2012b). It recommended that NERC "Support the development of improved Earth conductivity and ground impedance models for the North American geology" and set Task 1.7: "Finalize 1-D ground conductivity models". June followup reported:

Supporting tasks underway/completed:

- Ground conductivity model development: USGS has provided ground conductivity models and physiologic maps for some of the uniform conductivity regions in North America along with the 1-D conductivity models for each mapped region"

Ambiguities. EPRI's 2012 Report text is unclear whether Model NE-1 (Southern Maine) may represent upland as well as coastal Maine. USGS 2014a limits it to the coastal portion but stretches its reach to coastal New Hampshire, Massachusetts, Rhode Island, and Connecticut as well. In the case of BR-1 (Oregon), EPRI's 2012 Report at times also refers to "northeastern California" (a small area) and once, questionably, to "California" (which would be much larger, yet USGS 2014a picks that up).

Misinterpretations. USGS 2014a expands PT-1 and AP-2 regions to encompass the Blue Ridge and Valley and Ridge Provinces — unsupported interpretations of EPRI's 2012 Report akin to revisions.

3D MT data. Dr. Fernberg made some use of early MT measurements (for the Pacific Northwest) from the Earthscope array, which is providing data that can be used to construct 3D earth models with potential to improve on 1D calculation of electric fields as understanding evolves. (See Appendix D for his EarthScope MT array references.) His 2012 report noted "results from the EarthScope project, an extensive array of MT measurements being taken sequentially across the entire continental U.S., ... (Patro and Egbert 2008)" (at page 11-1), citing that source for deep resistivities in Tables 11-4 and 11-5 and shallow ones in text. Earlier, Dr. Fernberg and USGS considered having another Canadian expert prepare 3D modeling for the Pacific Northwest fraction of CONUS, but resources were not identified.

Sensitivity analysis. Dr. Fernberg did not secure resources to conduct sensitivity analyses.

Alaska. NERC's statutory authority to set (and FERC's to approve) reliability standards is limited to CONUS. That excludes Alaska. EPRI's 2012 Report deliberately covered five Alaska "zones" in its final Chapter 14. See Appendix E. NERC accidentally provided default scaling factors in TPL 7-001 Table 3 for some of those zones.

Roles of USGS. USGS's cooperation and growing interest in model validation ¹⁶ led NERC to call Dr. Fernberg's 2012 1D models USGS products (NERC 2013, page 7): "The US Geological Survey has produced a catalog of uniformly-layered earth models for the continental US [6 {citing EPRI's 2012 Report}]." Later regulatory filings called them 'publicly-available' earth models (NERC 2015, page 19).

Dr. Fernberg shared drafts with USGS (before EPRI editing). Had USGS had time and resources, it might conceivably have prepared an Open File Report for CONUS, in collaboration with Dr. Fernberg — as it did later for Model FL-1 alone, without him (USGS 2015). But that did not happen. EPRI published its 2012 Report before USGS could finish an Open File review process.

¹⁶ NERC and EPRI early recognized Dr. David Boteler of Natural Resources Canada as a GMD pioneer geophysicist who had communicated effectively with Canadian electric utilities. He participated in planning work when USGS did not (NERC GMDTF 2011). He was Dr. Fernberg's mentor (Fernberg 2011). In June 2011, NOAA SWPC suggested teaming to include USGS and NRCAN (NERC GMDTF 2011a). They also noted: "June __ Agreement with EPRI for support" and Pulkkinen et al. identified key geophysical factors that need to be addressed. USGS Geomagnetism's growing interest is reflected in USGS 2011, USGS 2012, USGS 2013, USGS 2013a. EPRI's 2012 Report acknowledged "support" of USGS and "assistance" of Drs. Boteler and Trichtchenko of the NRCAN Geomagnetic Laboratory.

EPRI 2014 status report. In 2014 EPRI reported its intention to potentially enhance the accuracy of earth conductivity/resistivity using a method of actually directly measuring the earth conductivity/resistivity during 2014-2015 (EPRI 2014, page 3-3). That did not happen then. Today, FERC, NERC, and EPRI assign high priority to improving ground conductivity models.

Conclusions. Dr. Fernberg, who produced all 1D models in EPRI's 2012 Report, explained limited extent of data. He omitted some regions altogether (e.g., Hudson River Valley, Ozark Plateau). He often stretched regions well beyond any model location (e.g., Model IP-1 in North Dakota stretched to Texas and Ohio and Model CP-2 in Georgia stretched to Texas and Arkansas). USGS, which contributed physiographic mapping to EPRI and NERC, later produced one 1D model (FL-1 for peninsular Florida) and prepared machine-readable interpretations of EPRI 1D models for NERC. These were steps in an evolving process of calculating and validating e-fields and better understanding vulnerabilities of electric bulk power supply, which suggest importance of completing 3D MT surveys (especially in regions of dense electric power infrastructure) and of resolving competing approaches to using them (USGS 2017). In the short run, some may exercise judgement to deviate from TPL 7's "beta" (β) scaling factors.

Acknowledgements. I acknowledge helpful conversations with and communications from Paul Bedrosian, David Boteler, Peter Fernberg, Carol Finn, Anna Kelbert, Jeffrey Love, Mark Olson, Tom Pruitt, Antti Pulkkinen, Josh Rigler, and other good teachers. I am solely responsible for all errors.

Appendices:

- A. Table comparing 71 traditional USGS with 19 EPRI / Fernberg and 20 NERC regions
- B. EPRI's own description of its 2012 Report.
- C. Excerpts from Dr. Fernberg's Introduction to 2012 EPRI Report
- D. Dr. Fernberg's References to EarthScope MT Survey in 2012 EPRI Report
- E. Fernberg, EPRI 2012 — Contents Summary

Appendix A. Table comparing 71 USGS with 19 EPRI / Fernberg and 20 NERC regions

71 USGS Physiographic Regions, provinces, sections	19 EPRI / Fernberg Regions (2012) 1D Model code - or "omitted"	20 NERC TPL 7 Table 3 (2015)	Bardin Comments
LAURENTIAN UPLAND			
1. Superior Upland	SU-1	SU1	USGS 2014a map deems south border ambiguous.
ATLANTIC PLAIN			
2. Continental Shelf (not on map)	Not on map	Not on map	
3. Coastal Plain			
a. Embayed section b. Sea Island section	CP-1 (South Carolina) CP-1 (South Carolina), CP-2 (Southern Georgia)	CP1 CP1, CP2	EPRI 2012 split province 3, shifting GA coast from 3.b. to CP-2.
c. Floridian section	CP-2 (Southern Georgia)	FL1 See USGS 2015	NERC created FL1 between ballots.
d. East Gulf Coastal Plain e. Mississippi Alluvial Plain f. West Gulf Coastal Plain	CP-2 (Southern Georgia) CP-2 (Southern Georgia) CP-2 (Southern Georgia)	CP2 CP2 CP2	EPRI 2012 lacked data for 3.c. d., e., f.
APPALACHIAN HIGHLANDS			
4. Piedmont province a. Piedmont Upland b. Piedmont Lowlands	PT-1	PT1	
5. Blue Ridge Province a., b. 6. Valley and Ridge Province a. Tennessee section b. Middle section c. Hudson Valley	Omitted Omitted Omitted Omitted Omitted	Omitted Omitted Omitted Omitted Omitted	USGS 2014a deemed PT-1 to cover province 5 & AP-2 to cover 6. EPRI 2012 did not say so.
8. Appalachian Plateaus province a. Mohawk section b. Catskill section c. Southern New York section	AP-2 AP-2 AP-2	AP2 AP2 AP2	
d. Allegheny Mountain section e. Kanawha section f. Cumberland Plateau section g. Cumberland Mountain section	AP-1 [EPRI table labeled it CP-1] AP-1 [EPRI table labeled it CP-1] AP-1 [EPRI table labeled it CP-1] AP-1 [EPRI table labeled it CP-1]	AP1 AP1 AP1 AP1	?
7. St. Lawrence Valley a. Champlain section	SL-1 St. Lawrence Valley	SL1	
b. Northern Section (not on map)	Not on map	Not on map	
9. New England Province a. Seaboard Lowland section b. New England Upland section c. White Mountain section d. Green Mountain section e. Taconic section	NE-1 (Maine) Omitted or NE-1 (Maine) ?? Omitted Omitted Omitted	NE1	Unclear whether all New England or even all ME is in NE-1. USGS 2014a thought only 9.a.
10. Adirondack province	AK-1A, AK-1B	AK1A, AK1B	

71 USGS Physiographic Regions, provinces, sections	19 EPRI / Fernberg Regions (2012) 1D Model code - or "omitted"	20 NERC TPL 7 Table 3 (2015)	Bardin Comments
INTERIOR PLAINS			
11. Interior Low Plateaus a. Highland Rim section b. Lexington Plain c. Nashville Basin	Omitted	Omitted	
12. Central Lowland a. Eastern Lake section b. Western Lake section c. Wisconsin Driftless section d. Till Plains e. Dissected Till Plains f. Osage Plains	IP-3 IP-1 (North Dakota) IP-1 (North Dakota) IP-1 (North Dakota) IP-1 (North Dakota) IP-1 (North Dakota)	IP3 IP1 IP1 IP1 IP1 IP1	
13. Great Plains province a. Missouri Plateau, glaciated b. Missouri Plateau, unglaciated c. Black Hills d. High Plains e. Plains Border f. Colorado Piedmont g. Raton section h. Pecos Valley i. Edwards Plateau j. Central Texas section	IP-4, IP-2 (North Dakota) IP-4, IP-2 (North Dakota) IP-4 IP-4 IP-4 IP-4 IP-4 IP-4 IP-4 IP-4 IP-4	IP4, IP2 IP4, IP2 IP4 IP4 IP4 IP4 IP4 IP4 IP4 IP4 IP4	
INTERIOR HIGHLANDS			
14. Ozark Plateaus a. Springfield-Salem Plateaus b. Boston "Mountains"	Omitted Omitted	Omitted Omitted	
15. Ouachita province a. Arkansas Valley b. Ouachita Mountains	Omitted Omitted	Omitted Omitted	
ROCKY MOUNTAIN SYSTEM			
16. Southern Rocky Mountains 17. Wyoming Basin 18. Middle Rocky Mountains 19. Northern Rocky Mountains	Omitted Omitted Omitted Omitted	Omitted Omitted Omitted Omitted	
INTERMONTANE PLATEAUS			
20. Columbia Plateau a. - e.	CO-1	CO1	
21. Colorado Plateaus a. - f.	CL-1	CL1	
22. Basin and Range Province a. Great Basin b. Sonoran Desert c. Salton Trough d. Mexican Highland e. Sacramento section	BR-1 (Oregon), rest Omitted ? Omitted ? Omitted ? Omitted ? Omitted ?	BR1	Unclear. Seems only OR part of 22.a. was included in BR-1 by EPRI 2012, none of 22.b., c., d., e. But USGS 2014a says Oregon & CA.

71 USGS Physiographic Regions, provinces, sections	19 EPRI / Fernberg Regions (2012) 1D Model code - or "omitted"	20 NERC TPL 7 Table 3 (2015)	Bardin Comments
PACIFIC MOUNTAIN SYSTEM			
23. Cascade-Sierra Mountains a. Northern Cascade Mountains b. Middle Cascade Mountains c. Southern Cascade Mountains d. Sierra Nevada	CS-1 (Oregon, Washington) CS-1 (Oregon, Washington) CS-1 (Oregon, Washington) Omitted ?	CS1	Unclear why CS-1 would extend to 23.d., for which EPRI 12012 acked data.
24. Pacific Border province	PB-2 (Puget Lowlands, Washington) PB-1 (Willamette Valley, Oregon)	PB2 PB1	See below.
a. Puget Trough b. Olympic Mountains c. Oregon Coast Range d. Klamath Range e. California Trough f. California Coast Ranges g. Los Angeles Ranges	PB-2 ? PB-2 ? PB-1 ? ? Omitted ? Omitted ? Omitted ?		Unclear how EPRI 2012 conductivity regions relate to USGS sections in OR or WA. Unclear why / whether they extend through CA.
25. Lower California province	Omitted	Omitted	

Appendix B: EPRI's own descriptions of its 2012 Report:

"Earth Conductivity Modeling Aids Scenario Definition and GIC Modeling

"An important part of defining the one-in-100-year scenario and in modeling GIC flows is the conductivity of the Earth, which can vary by orders of magnitude from one location to another. Determining the Earth conductivity for GIC analyses requires knowledge of the surface geology down to the deep crust and mantle of the Earth. The conductivity increases at greater depths within the earth's layers, where the pressure and the temperature also increase. Mineralogical changes also impact the level of conductivity, as some minerals are more conductive than others.

"The deep Earth soil *{sic}* conductivity is important because the skin depth of the return current can be tens of kilometers deep. This deep Earth conductivity drives the electric field. For a given storm magnetic field, lower conducting soil *{sic}* creates higher electric fields at the Earth's surface, which induces larger voltages in the transmission lines resulting in larger GICs.

"Although Earth's internal structure can have a complex three-dimensional distribution of electrical conductivity, the use of a one-dimensional (1D) model provides a useful first-order approximation for modeling gross conductivity structure and its effect on surface electric field in a particular region. A 1D model provides a general representation that shows the varying thickness of the Earth's crust and mantle to depths ranging from 600-1000 kilometers, as well as the conductivity of each layer.

"Peter Fernberg, an independent researcher from Ottawa, recently completed the development of many 1D models that show the Earth's conductivity for different physiographic regions (reflecting the bedrock geology) of the continental United States and Alaska. (This is part of a joint project between NERC, EPRI, the United States Geological Survey [USGS] Geomagnetism Program, National *{sic}* Resources Canada, and the USGS Crustal *{sic}*.) Natural Resources Canada and Professor Ian Ferguson at the University of Manitoba have already produced similar 1D models of Canada [2]. The 1D models were created using information gleaned from government reports and scientific journals, which include determinations of crustal and mantle thickness from seismic surveys and measurements of electrical conductivity using various geophysical survey methods such as magnetotellurics, which can map conductivity differences to depths of hundreds of kilometers. Additional models are being developed to provide a more complete picture of the US.

"The available 1D Earth conductivity models will be used with regional geomagnetic data to calculate the surface electric field for a particular region. The surface electric field values are then used as an input to EPRI's Open Source Distribution System Simulator (OpenDSS) to calculate the GIC that will be produced in the power grid ... "

—EPRI, *GMD News and Observer*, Issue 3, September 2012

For links to issues 1-10, see <https://www.epri.com/#/pages/product/3002004742/>.

"In research sponsored by EPRI along with NERC and U.S. and Canadian government support, Peter Fernberg, an independent researcher from Ottawa, completed the development of many 1D models that show the Earth's conductivity for different physiographic regions (reflecting the bedrock geology) of the continental United States and Alaska. (See EPRI Technical Update, "1D Earth Resistivity Models for Selected Areas of Continental United States and Alaska," 1026430, <http://www.epri.com/abstracts/Pages/ProductAbstract.aspx?ProductId=00000000001026430>)"

—EPRI, *GMD News and Observer*, Issue 4, April 2013

Appendix C: Excerpts from Dr. Fernberg's INTRODUCTION to 2012 EPRI Report:

"Objective and Scope

"This report presents one-dimensional (1D) Earth resistivity models for various physiographic regions (reflecting the bedrock geology) of the continental United States (see Figure 1-1 and Table 1-1) ... Each 1D model consists of a "layer-cake" figure showing the change of resistivity with depth, and a table detailing the information sources and justifications for the assigned conductivity/resistivity values and layer thicknesses. The values presented are based on the author's judgement and interpretation using publicly available information currently available and could conceivably change as a result of other interpretation or subsequent geophysical surveys.

Omissions, ambiguities in

EPRI's 2012 1D models

supporting NERC TPL7 β factor

“Nineteen models for selected continental United States physiographic areas were prepared,

“**Purpose of 1D Earth Resistivity Models**

“Numerical modeling of the effect of geomagnetically induced currents (GIC) in power transmission networks involves two components: geophysical and technological (Viljanen, 1989). The geophysical component deals with the calculation of a geoelectric field at locations along the transmission network; the technological component uses the geoelectric field as an input into a Direct Current (DC) system model. This calculates the GIC throughout the network. As a result, users can identify where on the network large GIC may occur and, combined with the statistics of geomagnetic activity, determine the magnitude and frequency of GIC events.

“The need for the geophysical component in the modeling process is due to the lack of regular recordings of the geoelectric field, either at geomagnetic observatories or along power transmission routes. Therefore, a geoelectric field has to be calculated, usually based on recordings of the geomagnetic field obtained from the closest geomagnetic observatory and application of the “plane wave” approach (Pulkkinen et al., 2001; Trichtchenko and Boteler, 2002). In this approach, the geomagnetic variations are regarded as a plane wave propagating downward into an Earth comprised of multiple horizontal layers of differing conductivity (inverse of resistivity) and thickness. Because the frequencies of natural geomagnetic variations are very low, ranging from millihertz to several Hz (Kaufmann and Keller, 1981), the penetration depth into Earth’s interior is very high (up to several 100s km depth). Thus deep geological conditions in the crust and mantle affect the surface geoelectric field. **{{N.B., Yellow circles mark where Dr. Fernberg’s data finds were concentrated rather than centers of physiographic regions.}}**

Figure 1-1
Location of 1D Earth Resistivity Models with Respect to Physiographic Regions of the Contiguous United States.

Table 1-1
Model Numbers for Each Physiographic Region (Chapter #s in Parentheses)

Model	Physiographic Description	Model	Physiographic Description
AK-1	Adirondack Mountains (New York) (1)	IP-1	Interior Plains (North Dakota) (8)
AP-1	Appalachian Plateau (5)	IP-2	Interior Plains (North American Conductive Anomaly) (8)
AP-2	Appalachian Plateau (Northern Portion) (6)	IP-3	Interior Plains (Michigan) (9)
BR-1	Northwest Basin and Range (Oregon) (11)	IP-4	Interior Plains (Great Plains Province) (13)
CL-1	Colorado Plateau (12)	NE-1	New England (Maine) (4)
CO-1	Columbia Plateau (11)	PB-1	Pacific Border (Willamette Valley, Oregon) (11)
CP-1	Coastal Plain (South Carolina) (5)	PB-2	Pacific Border (Puget Lowlands, Washington) (11)
CP-2	Coastal Plain (Georgia) (7)	PT-1	Piedmont (5)
CS-1	Cascade-Sierra Mountains (Oregon, Washington) (11)	SL-1	St. Lawrence Lowlands (New York) (3)
		SU-1	Superior Uplands (Minnesota, Wisconsin, Upper Michigan) (10)

{Fig. 1-2 omitted.} “The Earth’s internal structure can have a complex three-dimensional distribution of electrical resistivity. A one-dimensional (1D) model provides a useful first-order approximation for modeling gross resistivity structure and its effect on surface electric field in a particular region.

“Given that the conductivity (or its inverse, resistivity) structure of the Earth down to hundreds of kilometers affects the geoelectric field at the Earth’s surface, knowledge of both surface geology and the deep crust and mantle of the Earth is needed. For example, the Precambrian crystalline bedrock in Minnesota has a higher resistivity than the younger sedimentary rock that makes up the top layer of the Earth in Oklahoma. With ever increasing depth into the Earth, the pressure and temperature changes cause the resistivity to decrease. Mineralogical changes also affect resistivity. The combined information about all layers comprising Earth’s internal structure is used to determine the surface impedance of the Earth. This is then used with geomagnetic data to calculate the geoelectric field; which, in turn, provides the input into a DC system model for calculating GIC.

“**Earth Structure and the 1D Model**

“A 1D Earth resistivity model is comprised of a series of layers, showing the thickness and electrical resistivity, extending from the Earth’s surface through the crust and into the mantle (see Figure 1-3) where resistivity changes as a function of depth. From the surface downward, the layers are: unconsolidated overburden (e.g., glacially deposited sediments and residual material from degradation of bedrock); sedimentary cover rock (basin); upper crust (sedimentary, igneous, and/or metamorphic rocks) further divisible into upper, middle and lower zones; and upper mantle, transition zone and lower mantle. Mantle and transition (approximately 400 to 600 km) divisions reflect significant physical and mineral differences, which affect the electrical resistivity. A sedimentary basin is considered as a separate homogenous layer due to its typical low resistivity and approximate 1D structure (flat to gently dipping layers of rock over a large extent) although it is part of the upper crust. {Fig. 1-3 omitted.}

“An important assumption is that the resistivity and layer thickness is the same over the entire 1D model geographical area. On the scale of a continent, the model takes into account the lateral variations of resistivity by the changes between different Earth resistivity models for each physiographic region and/or tectonic terrane (or fragment of crustal material from one tectonic plate accreted to another plate).

“Continental crust in North America generally ranges from a thickness of 25 to 50 km, and can be divided into three geologically and geophysically distinct layers (Ferguson and Odwar, 1998). The upper crust, extending from the surface to a depth of 10 to 15 km is electrically resistive as it is commonly comprised of igneous and metamorphic rocks. Some areas of North America upper crust, such as the prairie states and eastern coastal plains, are covered by sedimentary rock, several 100 m to a few km thick and of considerably less resistivity than underlying crystalline rock. The middle crust, from the base of the upper crust to a depth of typically 25 km, is usually less resistive than the upper crust. The higher conductivity is interpreted to be due to accumulation of water released from metamorphic reactions. The lower crust is usually more resistive than the mid crust but less resistive than the underlying uppermost mantle.

“Anomalous high conductivity (i.e., low resistivity) zones can exist in the upper to mid-crustal rocks. Geological units and shear zones may contain concentrations of interconnected graphite and/or sapphires, which may substantially reduce the electrical resistivity in a local area. For example, the North American Central Plains (NACP) anomaly is a 2000 km long, narrow, highly conductive feature beginning in Wyoming and running across the Dakotas into northern Canada.

“Gross lateral changes in the Earth’s underlying geology can be accommodated by preparing individual 1D models for different regions of the continental United States. Often the physiographic changes across the country reflect the overall underlying geology that can be markedly different from a neighboring physiographic region. The gross geology is reflected in a distinctive overall electrical resistivity, which is most likely different from that of other physiographic regions. For example, the Interior Plain of the Mid-Western states consists of underlying

near-horizontal sedimentary rock ranging from 100s of meters to several km thick on a stable ancient continental crust exhibiting resistivity values typically in the 10s to low 100s of ohm-meters; by contrast, the Pacific Mountain System is made up of a variety of crystalline rock with resistivity values into the 1000s of ohm-meters.

“Sources of Information

“The 1D models were created using information compiled from government reports and scientific journals, which include determinations of crustal and mantle thickness from seismic surveys and measurements of electrical resistivity/conductivity using various geophysical survey methods such as magnetotellurics (MT). MT is a passive electromagnetic (EM) geophysical method that records the natural geoelectric and geomagnetic fields covering a frequency range between 0.0001 to 10,000 Hz, which equates to a signal penetration from shallow crust to upper mantle depths.

“The author emphasized using apparent electrical resistivity values obtained from MT surveys conducted as part of crustal investigations because such a value would represent the bulk resistivity of the Earth material over a large area. However, MT crustal transects tend to be focused on areas of geological interest, such as subduction zones and regional structures where the resistivity of the surrounding upper crust could be greatly modified compared to areas less affected. Where available and appropriate, induction logs from groundwater wells and hydrocarbon exploration wells were also examined to obtain near-surface electrical resistivity values, ...

“Layer depths for overburden in the continental U.S. and Alaska were obtained from surficial geology maps that provide general estimates of deposit thickness. Resistivity values of the overburden were obtained from groundwater-well geophysical logs or near-surface electrical resistivity surveys usually completed for geotechnical engineering purposes.

“Selection of a resistivity value for the upper crust layer can be problematic because overall resistivity is dependent on the most common rock types present, the degree of metamorphism and structural complexity, and the availability of interpreted MT data. Lower layers of an Earth resistivity model, comprising the mantle, tend to be more homogenous over a broader scale. Additionally, because the resolution of MT data decreases with depth the changes of resistivity between adjacent Earth resistivity models along a power-transmission route are greater for the upper layers than for deeper layers. The end result is greater non-uniformity of resistivity in the upper crust layer along the route.

“Resistivity values and layer thicknesses for the upper part of the 1D models, usually to depths less than 40 km, were obtained from geophysical transects in a particular area of the country. For the mid-to-lower crust and mantle, the author assumed that the resistivity does not vary significantly, and therefore resistivity values obtained from a crustal transect can be extended to areas on the route (or physiographic region) distant from the actual transect location where the MT sounding was made. For some of the 1D models mid-to-lower crust and mantle resistivities were extrapolated from regional MT surveys often quite distant to the location of the 1D Earth resistivity model. For divisions of the deeper Earth layers, the North American regional or Canada region conductivity profiles that Kelbert et al. (2009, Figure 2) compiled were used. The latter were derived from geomagnetic induction studies.”

Appendix D: Dr. Fernberg’s References to EarthScope MT Survey in 2012 EPRI Report:

[Chapter 11] NORTHWEST STATES (MODELS PB-1, PB-2, CS-1, CO-1 AND BR-1): WASHINGTON, OREGON, AND SOUTHWEST IDAHO. {See map below from Figure 11-6.}

“... Many regional MT profiles were undertaken the 1980s in the northwestern states region,

Preliminary results from the EarthScope project, an extensive array of MT measurements being taken sequentially across the entire continental U.S., are now forthcoming (Patro and Egbert, 2008). The 3D resistivity image of the Pacific Northwest compiled by Patro and Egbert (2008) extends to a 100 km depth.

“As summarized by Patro and Egbert (2008), the resistivity differences in the Northwest can be described as follows:

“An extensive lower crustal conductor (i.e., low resistivity) underlies southeast Oregon and southwest Idaho. The conductor is about 15 km thick with a top around 20 km deep, and is particularly conductive under the Northwestern Basin and Range (model BR-1). The high conductivity is attributed to presence of fluids – possibly due to partial melting at depth – associated with magma ponding and tectonic extension beneath the Basin and Range.

.... “Patro and Egbert (2008) show an elongate conductive zone (<10 ohm-meter) in the lower crust that follows the axis of the Cascade range in Oregon, but which also extends into the mid/upper crust in Washington to merge with the SWCC. Patro and Egbert remark that the shallow part of the SWCC was interpreted to be sediments tectonically accreted to the early North American continent, however the release of fluids and/or partial melting associated with subduction and magmatism beneath the Cascades may be the causes of the conductive zone at depth (Hill et al., Patro and Egbert).

.... “Between depths of 15 and 100 km, this author used an average of the 1D conductivity profiles prepared by Patro and Egbert (2008, Figure 3) for the Columbia Plateau, High Lava Plains, and Blue Mountains physiographic provinces. Patro and Egbert have shown that the mantle beneath the High Lava Plains and Blue Mountains exhibit a lower resistivity (<30 ohm-meter) compared to the more resistive Columbia Plateau, and they suggested it is the result of partial melts. Accordingly, a lower resistivity of 150 ohm-meter was assigned to the 100 to 150 km depth in contrast to the regional resistivity of 210 ohm-meter compiled by Kelbert et al. (2009). The 150 ohm-meter assigned value is roughly midpoint between 30 (from Patro and Egbert) and 250 ohm-meter (from Soyer and Unsworth).

“The assembly of model BR-1, down to a depth of 12 km, used resistivity across the northwestern portion of the Basin and Range province from Stanley et al.’s (1990, Figure 7, Profile GG’). Between depths of 8 and 100 km, this author used the 1D conductivity profile prepared by Patro and Egbert (2008, Figure 3) for the northwest Basin and Range physiographic province. The information provided the best resolution of resistivity showing the presence of the lower crustal conductor at 20 km depth. This conductive feature extends beneath the northwest Basin and Range, High Lava Plains, western part of the Snake River Plain, and the Blue Mountains, and is thought to represent the southern boundary of oceanic accreted terrane (Patro and Egbert, 2008).

“Patro, P. K. and Egbert, G. D., 2008. “Regional conductivity structure of Cascadia: Preliminary results from 3D inversion of U.S. array transportable array magnetotelluric data,” *Geophysical Research Letters*, v. 35, L20311-L20316. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1029/2008GL035326>.”

{Note — Patro and Egbert (2008), Abstract and Figs. 1 and 2 follow:}

“[1] In conjunction with the USArray component of EarthScope, long period magnetotelluric (MT) data are being acquired in a series of arrays ... Initial deployments in 2006 and 2007 acquired data (10–10,000 s) at 110 sites covering the US Pacific Northwest, distributed with the same

nominal spacing as the USArray seismic transportable array (~75 km). The most striking and robust features revealed by initial three-

Figure 1.
Open in figure viewer
Location of MT sites collected in 2006 (blue stars) and 2007 (red stars) on a map of physiographic provinces [after Rosefeldt, 1985]. Black arrows give geoelectric strike directions determined by fitting the distortion model of Smith (1997) for periods of 1000-10000 s. The top inset shows the distribution of strike directions, which have a 90° ambiguity. The bottom inset is a rose diagram for real induction vectors, which point towards conductive features, for a period of 1002 s.

Figure 2.

[Open in figure viewer](#)

3D resistivity image of the Pacific Northwest USA derived from the 3D inversion, plotted as slices of (left) constant depth and (right) constant latitude. Slab geometry from McCroly *et al.* [2003]. A: conductive zone in the forearc; C1-C6 and R1-R2 conductive and resistive features discussed in the text.

dimensional inversion all of southeastern Oregon.”

of this dataset are extensive areas of high conductivity in the lower crust beneath

Appendix E. FERNBERG, EPRI 2012 — Contents Summary

Chap.	Region	Models	PDF pages
1	Introduction		17-26 10
2	Adirondacks	AK-1A, AK-1B	27-33 7
3	St. Lawrence Lowlands	SL-1 : Upper New York State	35-40 6
4	New England	NE-1 : Southern Maine	41-47 7
5	Southeastern Appalachians	CP-1, PT-1, AP-1 : The Carolinas, Tennessee, Kentucky	49-60 12
6	Appalachian Plateau, Northern Part	AP-2 :south-central New York State	61-66 6
7	Coastal Plain	CP-2 :southern Georgia	67-73 7
8	Interior Plains	IP-1, IP-2 :North Dakota	75-86 12
9	Interior Plains	IP-3 :lower Michigan and eastern Wisconsin	87-96 10
10	Superior Upland	SU-1 :northern Minnesota, northern Wisconsin, and the upper Michigan peninsula	97-104 8
11	Northwest States	PB-1, PB-2, CS-1, CO-1, BR-1 : Washington, Oregon, and southwest Idaho	105-134 30
12	Colorado Plateau	CO-1 :southeastern Utah, northern Arizona, northwestern New Mexico, and western Colorado	135-140 6
13	Interior Plains - Great Plains Province	IP-4 :eastern Colorado, western Kansas, Texas panhandle, and southeastern New Mexico	141-148 8
14	Alaska - Zones 1 to 5		149-174 26
	A Bibliography		175-189 15

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Glossary:

- 1D One dimensional. Depth only.
- 2D Two dimensional. Depth plus transect or profile.
- 3D Three dimensional.
- 2012 EPRI Report *One-Dimensional Earth Resistivity Models for Selected Areas of Continental United States and Alaska*. EPRI, Palo Alto, CA: 2012. Technical Update. 1026430.
- CONUS Contiguous United States. Includes 48 states and District of Columbia. Excludes Alaska, Hawaii, and the territories.
- DOE U.S. Department of Energy
- EPRI Electric Power Research Institute
- FERC Federal Energy Regulatory Commission
- GICs Geomagnetically induced currents
- GMD Geomagnetic disturbances. GMDTF = NERC’s GMD Task Force, endorsed November 2010
- MT Magnetotelluric
- NASA National Aeronautics and Space Administration
- NERC North American Electric Reliability Corporation
- NOAA National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) which operates the Space Weather Prediction Center (SWPC)
- NRCan Natural Resources Canada
- USGS United States Geological Survey, which includes both Geomagnetism Program and Crustal Geophysics and Geochemistry Science Center